

How Do Humans and Computers Perform Differently in Site Selection? Insights from an Ambulance Station Placement Game.

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Abstract

This study explores the integration of human decision-making and computational optimization in emergency response system deployment (ERSD), using a novel interactive game-based approach. Players of the interactive game place configurations of ambulance stations (AS) on a map, attempting to maximize ambulance coverage within the area of the map. We analyze these configurations, contrasting them with an optimized computer-generated configuration. Our analysis includes a heatmap to visualize the spatial distribution of the configurations, Hausdorff distance calculations for configuration similarity, Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) for dimension reduction, and hierarchical agglomerative clustering. Additionally, medoid analysis identifies representative AS placements within clusters. Results yield intriguing differences between human intuition and the computational outcome, revealing potential implications for enhancing ERSD through hybrid models incorporating knowledge-based and data-driven approaches.

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1 Introduction

Planning emergency response system deployment (ERSD) is a pivotal challenge at the crossroads of urban development and public health management. In this context, the application of spatial information theory—particularly principles from spatial cognition and reasoning—is essential, as it provides a framework for understanding how spatial data and human decision-making interact to optimize the allocation of these systems [3, 4, 6, 8, 10]. By refining the ways we process and use geospatial data, spatial information theory not only deepens our understanding but also enhances our capacity to develop tactics that optimize ambulance coverage and response times in diverse urban settings. Such efforts are crucial for translating theoretical insights into practical tools that optimize ERSD.

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In response to these challenges, an interactive ambulance station (AS) placement game was developed—merging the analytical depth of geospatial computation and the capabilities of computer vision with the interactive appeal of augmented reality. This game illuminates the complexities of optimizing AS placements and serves as a didactic tool, educating users on the subtleties of geospatial data interpretation. Initially showcased at the 18th International Conference on Location Based Services [2], it represents a step forward in geospatial knowledge acquisition and its application in real-world problem-solving.

The present paper aims to dissect the insights from the gameplay data, briefly providing the game’s operational mechanics. Specifically, we seek to answer the question: How do human-generated ambulance station placement configurations compare to computationally optimized configurations in terms of performance measures such as population coverage within a specific time frame? We further examine the spatial decision-making patterns of players, contrasting human-derived tactics with those generated by computational optimization. In doing so, we aim to uncover the potential gaps in AS placement tactics and identify opportunities where computers can augment human decision-making. By structuring our analysis around heatmap visualization, similarity computation, dimension reduction, and clustering, we present a comprehensive analysis of spatial patterns and decision-making efficacies. The discussion sheds light on the implications of our findings but also contemplates the broader impact and how these insights can contribute to the development of hybrid models that combine human intuition and computational optimization in ERSD.

2 Methods

2.1 Game Mechanics

The game employs an interactive setup featuring a detailed map (of the road network, built-up area, population, and toponyms) of the Belgian province of East Flanders to simulate ambulance deployment. Participants included LBS conference visitors, prospective secondary school students interested in studying geography, staff members from our geography department, and attendees from the general audience of a "Day of Science" event. This map provides game players with contextual information to make informed decisions. Participants use ten blue magnets to represent potential AS, placing them on the map. A camera-projector system then captures the positions of these magnets, with the placement data processed in real-time. Using the OpenCV library [1], the system translates these positions into real-world coordinates, which are then used to calculate service areas for ambulances. These calculations consider population density and travel times, optimizing coverage for higher-density areas. The resulting service areas are visualized on the map through a projector, marking accessible areas green and inaccessible ones red, providing players with immediate feedback on their choices (see Figure 1). This setup educates participants on geospatial data interpretation. Also, it allows them to iteratively adjust their tactics based on the visualized outcome and a scoreboard that displays a score as the percentage of the population each configuration can serve. For a detailed description of the procedural intricacies of the game, refer to [2].

2.2 Data Collection and Preparation

Following gameplay, the placements made by each participant ($n = 457$), signified by the positioning of ten blue magnets, were collected and stored in a MultiPoint vector format. This approach directly translates each unique combination of placements into a configuration of geospatial coordinates, representing potential AS determined by the participants. In

■ **Figure 1** The game set-up: accessible regions are illuminated in green, and inaccessible regions are highlighted in red. The blue magnets represent the ambulance stations.

■ **Figure 2** KDE heatmap of ambulance station configurations with an overlay of the computer-generated configuration.

■ **Listing 1** Pseudo-code for the Local Optimization Algorithm

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Initialize with 10 randomly placed points
Repeat
  For each point:
    Evaluate shifts in 6 adjacent hexagonal cells
    Compute coverage for each possible shift
  End For
  Update configuration to the one with maximum coverage
Until no improvement in coverage is achieved
Output the optimal ambulance station configuration

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addition, a configuration with the best possible gameplay score was pursued using a heuristic optimization approach, which is a variant of the hill climbing algorithm (see Listing 1). The heuristic was optimized to maximize population coverage within a specific time frame, considering factors such as population density and travel times. However, as typical with heuristic methods, the algorithm might converge on a local optimum, depending on the initial placement of points and specific search dynamics. The process repeats until no further improvements can be made, yielding a locally optimal AS configuration. Subsequently, this computer-derived optimal configuration, alongside player-generated configurations, is compiled into a MultiPoint vector geometry for cluster analysis. This setup facilitates an examination of the nuanced interplay between human intuition and computational optimization in AS deployment strategies across East Flanders.

2.3 Heatmap Analysis

A Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) heatmap was generated to visualize the spatial distribution of all configurations. This technique allowed assessing areas with higher concentrations of proposed AS. Subsequently, the computer-generated configuration was overlaid on this heatmap. This step was crucial for visually comparing the collective spatial tendencies of human-made decisions against the heuristically derived computer configuration, providing initial insight into potential patterns for further cluster analysis.

2.4 Cluster Analysis

Similarity Computation

To discern the underlying patterns in the spatial tactics adopted by participants, we initiated our cluster analysis by comparing all configurations to identify similarities among them. We employed the Hausdorff distance—a robust and well-regarded metric in spatial analysis—known for its effectiveness in evaluating the topological similarity between individual configurations [5, 12]. This measure computes the maximum distance from a point in one configuration to the nearest point in the other configuration, thereby capturing the extent to which one configuration deviates from another. Specifically, we calculated the directed Hausdorff distance from each configuration to the other and took the maximum of these two values. This ensured that the similarity measure is symmetric and reflects the maximum extent of deviation between any two configurations, providing a comprehensive and balanced evaluation of similarity.

Dimension Reduction and Clustering

For the cluster analysis, we used Ward’s hierarchical method [13] on the Hausdorff distance matrix to identify potential configuration groupings based on their spatial similarities. A dendrogram, depicted alongside the color-coded distance matrix, provided a preliminary view of how configurations clustered together, guiding the determination of an appropriate number of clusters for further analysis. Following this phase, we applied dimension reduction to the dissimilarity matrix using Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP). This technique was chosen for its effectiveness in preserving both the global and local structure of high-dimensional data [7]. The UMAP embeddings reduced the dataset to a 2D space, making it suitable for visual analysis and clustering. Building on the insights from the dendrogram, we performed the hierarchical agglomerative clustering again, this time on the UMAP-reduced data, to definitively categorize the configurations into distinct clusters. The UMAP embeddings, colored by cluster labels, paved the way for a nuanced visualization of clusters through a 2D scatter plot. Using a discrete color map ensured clear differentiation between clusters, while the scatter plot highlighted the distribution of human-generated configurations and the distinct position of the computer configuration.

Medoid Analysis

Ultimately, the medoid was identified to capture the essence of each cluster. A medoid is defined as the configuration within the cluster whose sum of dissimilarities to all other configurations in the same cluster is minimal, making it the most representative or centrally located configuration [11]. This ensures a comprehensive representation of diverse AS placement tactics across the study area. The medoid configurations were visualized on a map of East Flanders. Each medoid was plotted using the same color scheme as in the UMAP cluster visualization, providing a visual link between the abstract UMAP embedding and the concrete geographic locations of AS. This medoid analysis highlighted the central tendencies within each cluster and facilitated comparison across clusters and with the computer-generated configuration. By visualizing these key configurations within the study area, we were able to ground our cluster analysis in a real-world spatial context, offering tangible insights into optimal AS deployment tactics.

■ **Figure 3** Color-coded normalized Hausdorff distance matrix and dendrogram. The red annotation indicates the position of the computer configuration.

■ **Figure 4** UMAP embedding of ambulance station placement configurations highlighting cluster distributions.

3 Results

This section presents the findings from our analysis as derived from the game data. We first explore spatial distribution patterns through a KDE heatmap, then assess configuration similarities with a dendrogram and distance matrix, delve into dimension reduction via UMAP, perform hierarchical agglomerative clustering, and conduct a medoid analysis to identify representative tactics within each cluster. Each subsection is supported by visual evidence, facilitating an understanding of the spatial dynamics at play.

3.1 Heatmap Analysis

The analysis started with a KDE heatmap to visualize the concentration of all proposed AS placement configurations (Figure 2). The map unveiled key areas of high and low participant engagement across the study area, with notable hotspots around the province capital of Ghent (270,000 inhabitants), as well as around cities such as Aalst (90,000 inhabitants), Sint-Niklaas (81,000 inhabitants), Dendermonde (50,000 inhabitants), and Oudenaarde (32,000 inhabitants). Overlaying the computer-generated optimal configuration on the heatmap revealed initial discrepancies between human and computational tactics. Notably, several points in the computer configuration were situated distinctly apart from the identified hotspots, indicating divergent placement priorities.

3.2 Cluster Analysis

Similarity Computation

The dendrogram, accompanied by the color-coded normalized Hausdorff distance matrix, revealed some first underlying patterns in configuration groupings (Figure 3). Three main clusters appear, with a potentially meaningful subdivision at six clusters to be observed. The computer configuration was annotated in red, appearing in the middle of the distance matrix, at the left edge of the third of six clusters. This approach provided a clear visual representation of configuration similarities and differences, guiding our clustering methodology.

Dimension Reduction and Clustering

Dimension reduction using UMAP provided an additional display of the complex data in a 2D scatter plot (Figure 4). From the dendrogram, six distinct sub-clusters emerged. Upon inspecting the UMAP embedding, it was clear that the computer configuration (together with some other human configurations) appeared in the rather isolated gray cluster 5. The configurations in clusters 3 and 4 each appear to be quite dissimilar from the rest and from each other. The other clusters (0, 1, and 2) have the most configurations and appear more grouped and central in the UMAP embedding.

Medoid Analysis

Ultimately, we identified and visualized medoids for each cluster, presenting a geographic ground truth of predominant AS placement tactics (Figure 5). Each subplot illustrates the diverse tactical insights. The visualizations, aligned with UMAP cluster colors for consistency, link to the analytical findings and their geographic implications.

Notably, cluster 4's configurations are characterized by their central concentration of AS, suggesting a preference for deploying resources within the heart of urban areas such as Ghent. This tactic contrasts sharply with the approach in cluster 5, which includes the computer-generated configuration. The medoid for cluster 5 displays a preference for placing AS near critical road axes, reflecting a focus on optimizing coverage through connectivity rather than urban density. This approach emphasizes enhanced accessibility from urban centers like Sint-Niklaas, Lokeren (43,000 inhabitants), and Ninove (40,000 inhabitants).

However, the computer-generated configuration within cluster 5 notably diverges even further from typical human strategies. It avoids dense urban centers, instead opting for more evenly distributed placements between key cities along primary and secondary roads. This shift is not just about road connectivity but also about maximizing response capabilities in areas that are equidistant from multiple urban centers, thus potentially offering quicker overall response times across a wider area.

Clusters 0, 1, 2, and 3 exhibit configurations with multiple AS closely encircling Ghent and dispersing along the study area's periphery near cities such as Sint-Niklaas, Dendermonde, Aalst, and Oudenaarde. These clusters demonstrate a mix of strategies that emphasize both urban concentration and regional coverage. Clusters 0 and 2 have the AS positioned typically near highways, whereas the AS in cluster 1 appear more near primary roads. Cluster 3 focuses on secondary roads, which might reflect a balanced approach to servicing urban and peri-urban areas.

The observations from the medoid maps align with the UMAP embedding analysis, where the computer configuration—and by extension, cluster 5—appears notably isolated, underscoring a computational strategy divergent from human intuition. Cluster 4 also emerges as distinct, reinforcing the diversity of approaches captured through the game. The UMAP embedding effectively groups configurations, yet the medoid analysis provides a granular view of how these groupings translate into spatial decisions.

4 Discussion

The analysis underscores the interplay between human intuition, computational optimization, and geographic context in ERSD. Through our data analysis—using a heatmap, cluster dendrogram, UMAP embedding, and medoid geographic distributions—we have uncovered notable variability in decision-making across clusters and distinct differences between human-

■ **Figure 5** Geographic distribution of cluster medoids for ambulance station placement tactics, with the computer-generated configuration added to cluster 5.

generated and computationally optimized configurations. While the differences between human and computer-generated configurations may seem apparent given the well-formulated nature of the problem, our study provides a systematic analysis of these differences and quantifies the variability in human decision-making patterns. This analysis is crucial for understanding the potential gaps in human intuition and identifying areas where computational optimization can complement human strategies.

Configurations in clusters such as cluster 4, which concentrate AS placements within urban areas, starkly contrast with those like cluster 5. This highlights a tendency of computational optimization to prioritize road connectivity over urban density, diverging from human tactics that often balance urban concentration with broader regional coverage.

The isolated positioning of the computer-generated configuration within the UMAP space further underscores its distinct approach. This positioning suggests that computational methods can deviate from human intuition, prioritizing a unique set of criteria that may not be immediately obvious to humans. This divergence raises pertinent questions about the comparability of human and computer-generated configurations, suggesting inherent differences between intuitive, knowledge-based decision-making and systematic, data-driven approaches. The insights gained from this study serve as a foundation for exploring hybrid models that leverage the strengths of both human intuition and computational optimization. By understanding the differences in decision-making patterns and the variability within human strategies, we can identify opportunities for developing collaborative human-computer systems that enhance ERSD decision-making. Future research can build upon these findings to investigate the effectiveness of hybrid approaches and their potential for improving emergency response outcomes.

Further enriching our analysis, integrating participant self-feedback on their placement choices could provide deeper insights into the cognitive processes influencing human tactics. Synthesizing these textual descriptions using language models could reveal underlying patterns in the thinking process, enhancing our understanding of spatial cognition within ERSD. Additionally, examining the adaptation of strategies across multiple gameplay attempts by the same participants will shed light on learning and tactical shifts over time. This

approach captures the immediate outcomes of individual game sessions and tracks how participants refine their strategies, offering a richer narrative on the evolution of decision-making in spatially complex environments. Future work might investigate how participants' age, gender, geospatial experience, and residency influence strategic choices, potentially explaining variations in gameplay across demographic groups. Expanding the dataset to include multiple computer-generated configurations would offer a more comprehensive reference set for comparison, improving the robustness and applicability of our findings. In addition, investigating the average scores per cluster and assessing the effectiveness of configurations close to the computer model could validate computational strategies.

The scalability and adaptability of our methods indicate they can be applied across various geographic settings, which validates the generalization of our analytical framework. We utilize the Hausdorff distance to quantify configuration similarities, while UMAP embeddings visually represent these relationships. UMAP's dimension reduction preserves topological relationships from the high-dimensional space in its lower-dimensional projection, suggesting that proximity in UMAP space indicates a strong similarity according to our metrics. However, it is vital to critically assess how we perceive these proximities, as cognitive biases can lead us to equate physical closeness in embeddings with actual similarity [9].

Ultimately, this study's findings have broader implications, opening avenues for future research that integrate human strategic insights with AI-driven optimization in ERSD. The insights gained from comparing human and computer-generated configurations can be used to develop hybrid models that leverage the strengths of both approaches. By understanding the differences in decision-making patterns, we can identify areas where human intuition and computational optimization can complement each other, leading to more effective and efficient ERSD. However, it is important to note that the participants in the study were from diverse backgrounds and may not represent the most optimal human performance in the domain. Similarly, the computational technique used, while providing a baseline for comparison, may not represent the state-of-the-art in computational optimization. Future research could focus on comparing the most optimal human performance, such as that of expert emergency response decision-makers, with the most advanced computational techniques. This approach would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential for hybrid human-computer placement strategies. This research contributes to the community's understanding of spatial decision-making in complex environments and highlights the potential for collaborative human-computer systems in addressing real-world challenges.

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